

1 **The transcriptional landscape of major depressive disorder (MDD), or severe major depression**
2 **(SMD) in humans.**

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7 We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in the brains of humans with major depression to
8 discover identifying components of the MDD gene signature in the CNS. In the ventral white matter of
9 humans with major depressive disorder, we observed strong transcriptional activation of the solute carrier
10 transporter *SLC1A5*.

11 Brain transcriptome: GSE248260

12 Blood transcriptome: GSE247998

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